

Advocating for Silver-Based Valuation in Zakat Computation: The Urgency of Adopting Silver Equivalents in Contemporary Muslim Societies

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Abstract

This paper makes a case for the urgent need for the adoption of silver-based valuation in zakat computation in our contemporary Muslim communities. Drawing upon historical precedent, Islamic jurisprudence, and modern economic realities, it establishes the fact that silver which has long been a foundational reference point for zakat assessment—provides a more inclusive and equitable standard than gold. By shifting to silver-based nisab (threshold), a broader segment of the Muslim population becomes zakat-liable, thus enhancing wealth redistribution and social welfare. The paper also clarifies common misconceptions relating to the use of silver-based nisab and provides policy recommendations for scholars, institutions, and governments to revive the social justice mission of zakat.

Keywords: *Nisab, dinar, dirham, zakat, caliph, maal*

Introduction

Zakat is the third pillar of Islam and a great means of financial empowerment and poverty reduction. The significance of zakat is not just in its being a pair-twin of salat (obligatory prayer), but the fact that it became one of the two reasons leading to the war of apostasy (riddah) for which Abubakr, the first caliph had to raise an army of mujahidun (Islamic soldiers) to combat. Apart from the reasons that some supposedly Muslims had begun to apostatized by recognizing certain impostors as messengers of Allah, some others had vowed to stop their remittance of zakat to baytul maal (Islamic treasury). This was despite the fact that the number of participating mujahidun who had memorized the entire Quran is threatened to be reduced as a result of suffering martyrdom in these expeditions. Abubakr nevertheless was resolved to confronting this heresy saying:

“By Allah, surely I will most certainly fight those who separate prayer and zakat, for zakat is what is due on wealth. By Allah, if they withhold from me a rope which they used to pay to the messenger of Allah, I will fight them for it”. (Tarikh Khulafa p.60).

As a required condition for the payment of zakat, Islam stipulates that the maal (wealth/property) intended for this purpose must have reached the required nisab threshold. The nisab is the minimum amount of wealth upon which zakat becomes obligatory. For instance, in relation to livestock the nisab in the case of camel is 5. This means that among other notable conditions, the number of camels must be 5 before zakat becomes due. In the same vein, the nisab for cow is 30 while that of sheep is 40.

In relation to money however, it must be noted that people in the earliest times were not used to currency dealings and exchange. They nevertheless transacted among themselves through the

medium of goods exchange or trade by barter. This went on until people gradually changed their method of dealing and settled for transacting in gold and silver due to what Allah has endowed these two of some special qualities above other precious materials (Tayyar, 2013).

In this respect, people were already used to gold and silver transactions during the period of revelation when prophet Muhammad was raised in the name of dinar (for gold currency) and dirham (for silver) respectively. Hence, Islam in its compatibility with all times and ages addressed the people accordingly in terms of their dealing with those two media of exchange; and instructed them to pay their zakat on them accordingly. It is based on this that scholars deduced that whatever becomes a medium of exchange (or currency) among any set of people at any particular point in time is to be assessed and calculated for zakat such as the Naira, Dollar, Euro, Pounds etc.

Unfortunately in many of our Muslim communities of today, the focus is only on gold based valuation. This has not only weakened zakat redistributive impact, but has also excluded many middle-income Muslims from the obligation of zakat. As a result, zakat collection is diminished, the aims unmet, the situation of the needy unchanged and the needs of the poor remain uncatered for.

This paper thus advocates for the recalibration of estimating zakat through the adoption of silver equivalents, particularly in low and middle-income economies such as ours. It draws upon historical jurisprudence, economic analysis, and ethical reasoning to argue that a silver-based approach not only aligns more closely with the spirit of Islamic social finance but also ensures a more effective and inclusive zakat system.

Evidence on the Obligation of Zakat On Money/Currency

There are specific evidences for the obligation of zakat on money in the Quran as well as prophetic Sunnah. More so, there is the consensus of Islamic scholars – past and present- on the obligation of zakat on currency used by any people (al-Ijma p31). The followings allude to that:

“As for those who hoard gold and silver and spend it not in the way of Allāh - give them tidings of a painful punishment. The Day when it {- The gold and silver which was hoarded, i.e., whose zakāh was not paid.} will be heated in the fire of Hell and seared therewith will be their foreheads, their flanks, and their backs, [it will be said], "This is what you hoarded for yourselves, so taste what you used to hoard." (Q9:34-35)

Abu Hurayrah reported Allah’s messenger as saying:

“No owner of gold or silver who fails to pay what is due on him, except that he will have sheets of fire made for him on the day of judgment. They will be heated in the hellfire then used to burn his sides, forehead and back. Whenever they get cool they are reheated to him in a day whose length is 50,000 years long until judgement is pronounced among the people and he is shown his path either to paradise or hell (Muslim, no. 987)

Aliy bn Abi Talib narrated from the messenger of Allah his saying:

“When you possess 200 dirhams and one year passes on them, 5 dirhams are payable. Nothing is incumbent on you, that is, on gold, till it reaches 20 dinars. When you possess 20 dinars and one year passes on them, half a dinar is payable” (Abu Dawud, no. 1558)

Abu Saeed said, Allah’s apostle said: *“No zakat is due on property amounting to less than 5 uqiyas (of silver)”* (Bukhari, 1484; Muslim, 979)

From the above stated evidences, the following becomes crystal clear:

- i) That it is a must to estimate and pay zakat on gold and silver money.
- ii) That serious torments await those who do not estimate or pay their zakat based on gold or silver currency despite having what amounts to nisab.
- iii) That the nisab on silver currency is 5 uqiyas which is 200 dirhams (this is equivalent to 595 grams of silver).
- iv) That the nisab on gold currency is 20 dinar (this is equivalent to 85 grams of gold).
- v) That a whole (hijrah) year must pass on the nisab before billing it for zakat.
- vi) That the amount payable on the zakatable money (gold or silver) is 2.5% (i.e. 5 dirhams in the case of silver and half dinar in the case of gold).

Illustrating this, if someone possesses 600 grams of silver, then the actual amount to be paid as zakat is 2.5% of 600 grams or $1/40 \times 600 = 15g$

In the case of gold, if someone possesses 90g, the actual amount payable is 2.25 grams of gold.

Contemporary Zakat Practices and Challenges

Modern zakat practices often rely on gold based nisab. Unfortunately however, due to the high market value of gold especially in modern time, many financially capable Muslims are excluded. Empirical evidences from Muslim majority countries like Nigeria, Pakistan, Indonesia show that silver-based valuation dramatically increases the number of zakat payers (Kamal, 1998; Mananu, R. et al, 2024)

A practically demonstrated case done with Peaceland Estate Muslim Community Ogombo, a moderate Islamic community in Lagos, in March 2025 revealed that the use of silver based nisab gave room for more and wider participation in zakat remittance as opposed to an only sole-gold based valuation which constricts its coverage. Thus, communities that switch to silver valuation report higher zakat inflows and wider support for welfare initiatives. This is more in tune and closer to the spirit of the verse urging the wealthy to ensure their wealth reaches the poor:

كَيْ لَا يَكُونَ دُولَةً بَيْنَ الْأَغْنِيَاءِ مِنْكُمْ

so that it will not be a perpetual distribution among the rich from among you (Q59:7)

Advocating for Silver Equivalence in Zakat Computation

Indeed, adopting silver-based nisab not only addresses our socio-financial gaps but also serves as a lasting solution to some key economic, ethical and practical issues:

1. Economic Rationale: The economic rationale for the use of silver-based nisab lies in the fact that silver's lower market value (in comparison with gold's super high market value) ensures that more Muslims with disposable income qualify for zakat. This broadens the payer base, increases the systems financial capacity and generally caters more for the need of the poor.

For instance, in our Nigeria of today, to be eligible to pay zakat based on gold valuation would require one to have N14,396,320 according to the National Moon Sighting Committee of the Nigeria Supreme Council for Islamic Affairs (NSCIA) as shared on its Facebook and twitter handles respectively, dated 23rd May, 2025. A vast majority of working class Muslims would be excluded from zakat payment going by this bogusly large amount considering the economic realities of present-day Nigeria. However, our independent calculation of the nisab based on silver valuation only amounts to N987,800. A very considerable amount which affordability is not far-fetched. How did we arrive at this?

In the previous hadith as quoted, Ali bn Abi Talib reported from the messenger of Allah thus:

“If you have 200 dirhams which has completed a term of one year, then 5 dirham is due.” (Abu Dawud, 1558)

According to modern jurists, one prophetic dirham equals 2.975 grams of silver (Al-Qardawiy,1969; Abdullah, 2020). Based on the *Nigeria Silver Price Live source*, the market price of 1 gram of silver is N1,660.17. This means that 2.975 of silver in Naira terms is: $2.975 \times 1660.17 = N4,939$.

Thus, based on the calculation that 1 dirham is N4,939; 200 dirhams which is the zakat nisab would therefore calculate as $4939 \times 200 = N987,800$.

In the light of this, the miqdar (actual zakat amount) payable which is rub'ul ushr (i.e. 2.5%) is N24,695 as at May, 2025

2. Ethical justification: Islam prioritizes collective welfare even when that conflicts with personal benefits. How much more when no harm is inflicted whatsoever (as in this case) on both the payer and the receiver. Using silver aligns with this priority by promoting broader participation and maximizing benefits to the poor.
3. Empirical support: Several case studies such as that of Peaceland Estate Muslim community, Ogombo conducted by this researcher as well as others such as Mananu et al (2024) validate the factual assertion and practical advantage of silver-based valuation over gold. Communities like PEMC and others who base their application on silver report significant improvement in zakat coverage and social welfare.

Counter-Argument and Responses

There are usually several concerns over the use of silver-based valuation for nisab. Such arguments are discussed below with corresponding and appropriate responses. Although these arguments may look valid superficially, there are appropriate mechanisms with which sharia has dealt with them, thus giving them no weight as to nullify the determination by silver equivalence:

1. The Concern of Over-Burdening the Poor

While some might think that using silver based nisab might overburden the lower income earners, there is already a provision in the Islamic jurisprudence which safeguards against this through exemption, based on basic needs and debts.

2. The Question of Gold Stability

Although gold is more stable, its exclusivity defeats the purpose of zakat which is to reduce poverty as much as possible. The sharia allows flexibility and the preference historically leaned towards whichever standard encompassed more people into the zakat paying fold. Thus, the criterion is what benefits the poor most.

3. Fear and Confusion

Legitimate fear, worries and confusion particularly among the masses could be mitigated by sound advocacy and public awareness. This could be done by ulamah on mimbars, special lectures, writings and publications etc. Rather than publishing only gold-based nisab amounts, Islamic bodies should publish dual nisab rates (showing silver as well), with clear justifications that can effectively guide the public.

Policy Implications and Recommendations

This paper suggests some recommendations and calls for some policy implementations by notable stakeholders – religious bodies, zakat institutions, Islamic scholars and preachers, governments and community leaders.

Religious organizations have a duty to sensitize their members especially the working class on the need to estimate their wealth using silver based nisab and encourage them to pay based on its overall advantage of reaching a wider recipient. Zakat institutions on the other hand must adopt silver in lower income context, and not limit their publications to gold nisab alone, but rather publish silver as well while simplifying calculation tools. On the part of Islamic scholars, they must continue to enlighten the people about the significance of zakat in Islam generally and about the urgency of caring for the needy and poor through an enlarge zakat payment system such as the use of silver based valuation in their regular Friday sermons, halaqat (circles of learning), academic dawrah (seminars and conferences) and other media of preaching. The government also should integrate silver-based zakat into national frameworks as it has done with sukuk; and use proceeds for public welfare. The community as well have a duty to support efforts in promoting awareness and accountability in zakat utilization.

Conclusion

The efficacy of zakat towards poverty alleviation is of no doubt. However, its effectiveness is compromised by rigid reliance on gold. Silver-based nisab offers an economically relevant, ethnically grounded and realistically viable alternative. By adopting silver as the standard especially in low and middle income contexts, Muslim communities can revitalize the role of zakat as an instrument of social welfare. This shift should not be seen as a break from the tradition but a revival of the true intent of zakat.

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